

AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

[IJMS] Submission Acknowledgement

1 message

Jayapangus Press <journalofmultidisciplinary@gmail.com>
To: Ahmad <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

Tue, Nov 28, 2023 at 3:54 PM

Ahmad:

Thank you for submitting the manuscript, "Gender, Ethnicity, Family Socio-Economics, and Grit (A Islamic Higher Education Students Context)" to International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences. With the online journal management system that we are using, you will be able to track its progress through the editorial process by logging in to the journal web site:

Submission URL: <https://jayapanguspress.penerbit.org/index.php/IJMS/authorDashboard/submission/2821>
Username: ahmadjuhaidi

If you have any questions, please contact me. Thank you for considering this journal as a venue for your work.

Jayapangus Press

[International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences](#)

[IJMS] Editor Decision

4 messages

Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>
To: Ahmad <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

Thu, Dec 7, 2023 at 8:38 PM

Ahmad:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences, "Gender, Ethnicity, Family Socio-Economics, and Grit (A Islamic Higher Education Students Context)".

Our decision is: Revisions Required

[International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences](#)

 A-Gender, Ethnicity, Family Socio-Economics, and Grit.docx
103K

AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>
To: Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>

Sat, Dec 9, 2023 at 8:04 AM

Dear Micheal James Kasozi

I want to thank the reviewers for their insightful feedback. All responses to comments from the Reviewer are highlighted in yellow in the main text. Please find attached the revised manuscript.

Thank you for considering my revised submission. We eagerly anticipate your feedback and hope for a favorable evaluation of the revised manuscript for possible publication in your esteemed journal.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Warm regards,

Ahmad Juhaidi

REVIEWER COMMENT

COMMENT#1

Grit refers to perseverance and passion in achieving a long-term goal. Although grit is regarded as a relatively stable trait, empirical studies also indicate that grit is malleable. Thus, documenting the role of grit in the association between teacher autonomy support and the social competence of undergraduate students is particularly valuable, as this finding may provide some possible insights into designing intervention or prevention studies. According to the extant literature, grit is positively linked to success within a broad range of academic settings, which has also been extended to college students. Despite such research progress, little attention has been paid to the possible linkage between grit and outcomes beyond academic settings. This must be taken into consideration in this research.

RESPONSE

The necessary additions have been made

COMMENT#2

Please correct this typing error

RESPONSE

Fixes have been made

COMMENT#3

You can summarize the description of this method again, just one or a paragraph.

RESPONSE

The necessary revisions have been made

COMMENT#4

It is important for you to provide a discussion referring to the results of previous research, including the theory used. Add references from journals.

RESPONSE

The necessary additions have been made

COMMENT#5

References are written using APA 6 style (for example, see the template).

RESPONSE

The necessary revisions have been made

COMMENT#6

Sources other than books or journals must be deleted.

RESPONSE

The necessary revisions have been made

[Quoted text hidden]

 REV1GritJMS.docx
93K

Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>
To: AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

Sat, Dec 9, 2023 at 10:54 AM

You can upload in revision (journal website)

[Quoted text hidden]

AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>
To: Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>

Sat, Dec 9, 2023 at 11:03 AM

yes .. i have done

[Quoted text hidden]

AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

[IJMS] Editor Decision

2 messages

Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>
To: Ahmad <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>

Mon, Dec 11, 2023 at 7:20 PM

Ahmad:

We have reached a decision regarding your submission to International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences, "Gender, Ethnicity, Family Socio-Economics, and Grit (A Islamic Higher Education Students Context)".

Our decision is to: Accept Submission

Next, please pay the article processing fee (APC) of Rp. 750,000.

Payment can be made by transfer to BCA Account No. 6690795599 a.n. JAYAPANGUS PRESS CV / BNI Account No. 0194823396 a.n. I Ketut Sudarsana

Proof of payment MUST be sent via email journalofmultidisciplinary@gmail.com

Best regards

Editor

[International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences](#)

AHMAD JUHAIDI <ahmadjuhaidi@uin-antasari.ac.id>
To: Micheal James Kasozi <mjkasozi@gmail.com>

Mon, Dec 11, 2023 at 8:47 PM

Dear Micheal James Kasozi

I hope this message finds you well. I am writing in response to the acceptance decision for my submission titled "Gender, Ethnicity, Family Socio-Economics, and Grit (An Islamic Higher Education Students Context)" in the International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences.

Firstly, I would like to express my gratitude for the acceptance and assure you of my commitment to promptly fulfill the payment of the article processing fee (APC) of Rp. 750,000. In addition to the payment, I am curious about the expected timeline for the publication of my manuscript. Your guidance on the expected publication timeline would be immensely appreciated. I am looking forward to seeing this research published in the esteemed International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences.

Thank you for your attention to this matter. I eagerly await your response.

Warm regards,

Ahmad Juhaidi
[Quoted text hidden]